

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

DDX1

(DEAD-box helicase 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

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Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

The TREAT-AD Center has developed an integrative target ranking score encompassing evidence of gene and protein involvement in AD from both genomics and genetics studies. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's disease (AD), and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available (1). Gene set enrichment analysis of all scored genes highlights the "innate immune response" Gene Ontology (GO) term as one of the most significantly enriched among genes with the highest Target Risk Score. This GO term was also identified through analysis of transcriptomic and proteomic pseudotime states (2) as being among the processes for which there is evidence of differential expression in early states of disease progression. Among the leading edge (i.e. top-scoring) genes in the "innate immune response" GO term were a set of RNA helicase proteins including IFIH1, DHX58, and DDX1. Network pathway modeling identified these as central nodes within the network related to innate immune response, and analysis of patient pseudotime indicates the expression of these genes changes in early disease pseudo-states. These targets were nominated within a hypothesis that over-activation of the innate immune response triggers aberrant cytokine signaling and excessive phagocytosis of synapses and neurons, leading to neurodegenerative pathogenesis in AD.

DDX1 has a TREAT-AD Target Risk Score (**Fig. 1A**) of 3.19 out of 5 (rank #3805, 84.8th percentile). The individual score components indicate a relatively stronger disease association based on genomics from postmortem brain than genetic studies, including 1.21 out of 3 for genetic risk (39th percentile) (**Fig. 1B**) and 1.98 out of 2 for genomic risk (97th percentile) (**Fig. 1C**). The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of DDX1 protein is significantly increased while DDX1 RNA is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD (**Fig. 1C**).

Cell-type specific expression of DDX1 was assessed using single-cell data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD) (sea-ad.org, (3)). The expression of DDX1 was averaged across cells within a supertype from each donor. The locally weighted mean expression (LOWESS) of superotypes within each subclass is then plotted across the range of continuous donor pseudo-progression, which orders subjects based on a learned model of neuropathological burden. DDX1 is ubiquitously expressed in all cell types measured in the SEA-AD dataset. DDX1 expression in neuronal subclasses decreases across donor pseudo-progression (**Fig. 1D**).

Figure 1. (A) DDX1 TREAT-AD Target Risk Score, and **(B)** component genetic risk score and **(C)** multi-omic risk score. The lines within the score and component score violin plots show the 50th and 90th percentile scores. **(D)** DDX1 cell-type expression data from SEA-AD. Cell type expression plots show the locally weighted mean expression of cell supertypes from each donor within each subclass along donor pseudo-progression.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (“biodomains”) (1). These biodomains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biodomains via GO term annotations. DDX1 is annotated to GO terms from 7 biodomains, primarily to terms from the RNA Spliceosome, Immune Response, and DNA Repair domains (**Fig. 2A**).

The CRISPRbrain resource (crisprbrain.org, (4)) is a data commons for functional genomics datasets from differentiated human iPSC derived cell types. The CRISPRbrain reports phenotype results following CRISPR screens of gene activation (CRISPRa), inhibition (CRISPRi), or gene knockout (CRISPRn), in iPSC derived brain-relevant cell types. Following the screens, genes are identified as either positive or negative hits, meaning perturbation leads to a significant and reproducible increase or decrease in the measured phenotype, respectively, or a non-hit if the perturbation does not significantly impact the phenotype. Inhibition of DDX1 in neurons leads to significantly lower tau oligomerization, decreased neuronal survival, and decreased peroxidized lipids, while inhibition of DDX1 in astrocytes leads to a reduction in lysosome exocytosis, as measured by cell surface expression of LAMP1 (**Fig. 2B**).

Figure 2. (A) DDX1 TREAT-AD biological domain annotations and **(B)** phenotypes from CRISPR screens in iPSC derived cell types from the CRISPRbrain resource

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Alzheimer’s disease (AD) is a debilitating brain disorder that affects over 6 million Americans, aged 65 and older with no known effective treatment to date. The past two decades of drug discovery efforts in AD have been focused on a few therapeutic hypotheses with little success in developing game-changing therapies for human use. To this end, the National Institute on Aging has launched the TREAT-AD initiative (TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for AD), which aims to improve and diversify the portfolio of AD drug targets by accelerating the characterization and experimental validation of next-generation therapeutic targets. Among others, the DDX1 helicase was nominated by the consortium to study its potential role in AD progression (<https://agora.adknowledgeportal.org/genes>). DDX1 is a member of DEAD box family of helicases and was shown to have ADP-dependent unwinding activity against dsRNA and DNA-RNA hybrids (5). DDX1 was shown to be overexpressed in retinoblastoma and neuroblastoma cell-lines (6,7). Here we aim to generate Target Enabling Packages (TEPs), including proteins, crystal structures and high-throughput biochemical activity assays to enable the discovery of small-molecule chemical probes to help evaluate the role of DDX1 in AD progression and its therapeutic potential.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

DDX1 is a member of the DEAD box family of RNA helicases, characterized by the conserved motif Asp-Glu-Ala-Asp (DEAD) (8). DDX1 is a 740-residue protein composed of two RecA-like domains as well as a unique insertion domain within the N-terminal RecA-like domain called SPRY (9). DDX1 was first identified to be overexpressed in several retinoblastoma and neuroblastoma cell-lines (6). It was later explored for its role

in different aspects of RNA metabolism, including pre-mRNA splicing and processing (10,11), RNA transport (12), and the maturation of micro-RNAs (13). Additionally, DDX1 has been suggested to play a role in the cellular repair response to double-strand breaks, revealing its RNase activity toward ssRNA, as well as ADP-dependent RNA-DNA- and dsRNA-unwinding activities (5). More studies subsequently suggested the diverse substrate specificities of DDX1 which include ssRNAs, dsRNAs, DNA-RNA hybrids, and G-quadruplexes (14,15).

Evidence has shown that the function of DDX1 could be important for viral replication as it is often inhibited/hijacked by viruses including coronavirus (16), HIV (17), and hepatitis C virus (18). Its role in the immune system was further validated when Zhang and colleagues identified the role of DDX1 as a cytosolic sensor for viral RNA, which upon recognition, forms a multi-helicase complex with DDX21 and DHX36 in myeloid dendritic cells (19). It was discovered that DDX1 interacts with DDX21 through its SPRY domain, while DDX21 bridges DDX1 and DHX36. The complex interacts with the adaptor protein TRIF to trigger an innate type I IFN immune response against poly(I:C). Subsequently, RNA-splicing ligase (RTCB) was shown to have an inhibitory effect on the type I IFN response triggered by poly(I:C) by directly interacting with DDX1 and impeding its binding with DDX21 (20).

Although the role of DDX1 in the nervous system is largely undiscovered, there is emerging evidence that links DDX1 to pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease and related dementia (ADRD). A gene analysis that utilizes inference of multiple differential modules and co-expression networks identified DDX1 to be important for the occurrence and development of AD (21). Furthermore, in a whole-exome sequencing (WES) study of 350,000 ADRD patients, DDX1 is among the seven novel genes that were identified to be differentially expressed in AD brains versus control (22). In combination to the unbiased target risk score from the Accelerating Medicines Partnership in AD (AMP-AD) program, which prioritized DDX1 as a high-confidence target (23), these genetic data provide a strong basis for further in vitro studies to elucidate the molecular mechanism underlying DDX1's involvement in AD.

Given that DDX1 participates in a wide array of cellular processes, it is essential to delineate which specific functions contribute to its involvement. For instance, one study has highlighted the potential role of DNA/RNA G-quadruplexes (G4) and G4-binding proteins, such as DDX1, in aging and AD (24). Another study suggests a neuroprotective role of DDX1, showing that it binds and protects RNAs that encode for proteins important for stress recovery and neuronal health (25). Lastly, the role of DDX1 in the innate immune system may be relevant to the viral hypothesis of AD, where certain types of infections contribute to disease pathogenesis (26).

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

Understanding the etiology of Alzheimer's disease (AD) requires a comprehensive molecular and biological investigation of the approximately 184 genes and corresponding proteins linked to AD risk. However, research efforts remain heavily skewed: just three genes—APP, APOE, and MAPT (tau)—account for 49% of all AD-related publications indexed on PubMed. This imbalance underscores the urgent need to expand the focus to include the broader landscape of AD-associated proteins.

A key barrier to this expansion is the limited availability of selective and renewable antibodies for many of these understudied proteins. The TREAT-AD program aims to address this gap by identifying or developing

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high-quality research tools for less-characterized AD-associated proteins, enabling rigorous hypothesis testing (23).

The Antibody Characterization through Open Science (YCharOS) initiative, led from McGill University, is a global, public-good effort uniting academic researchers, funding agencies, 13 leading antibody manufacturers, and two knockout cell line providers. Using industry-endorsed protocols (27), YCharOS systematically evaluates antibody performance with the goal of identifying one or more high-quality renewable antibodies (e.g., monoclonal or recombinant) per human protein target. Antibodies are tested side-by-side in immunoblot (western blot), immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using isogenic knockout cell lines as controls. All results are shared openly and rapidly via the AD Knowledge Portal (<https://adknowledgeportal.synapse.org/>) and in the Zenodo YCharOS community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/treatad/>).

Here, eleven DDX1 antibodies—sourced from six companies and spanning recombinant, monoclonal, and polyclonal formats—were evaluated using a DDX1 knockout cell line (commercially available from Abcam). While specific renewable antibodies suitable for immunoblot and immunoprecipitation were identified, none of the antibodies showed specificity in immunofluorescence. This characterization report provides researchers with data-driven guidance to select the most appropriate antibodies for studying DDX1, and is available on Zenodo. Complete report: [DDX1 antibody characterization report](#).

Protein constructs and expression methods: Proteins purified

1. Full-length His-tagged DDX1: Human full-length (aa1-740) DDX1. Contains an N-terminal His6 and TEV cleavage site. Protein produced in sf9 insect cells. Used in DSF and ATPase assay.
2. SPRY domain & C-terminus domain-truncated DDX1: Truncated construct (aa1-74; 286-674) of human DDX1 (Δ SPRY_CTD). His tag removed. Protein produced in sf9 insect cells. Used for crystallography.
3. RecA-like Domain N of DDX1: Truncated construct (aa1-74; 286-431) of human DDX1 (RecA-like N). His tag removed. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used in DSF.
4. RecA-like Domain C of DDX1: Truncated construct (aa433-674) of human DDX1 (RecA-like C). His tag removed. Protein produced in bacterial cells. Used in DSF.
5. Full-length biotinylated DDX1: Human full-length (aa1-740) biotinylated DDX1. Contains an N-terminal AviTag biotinylation signal and a C-terminal His6 tag. Protein produced in sf9 insect cells. Used in SPR.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

Crystal Structure

The SPRY and CTD truncated variant of DDX1 (aa286-674) was cloned and purified to facilitate crystallization and structural determination of the helicase domain of DDX1 and assist with future structure-guided drug discovery efforts. The crystals diffracted to 2.7Å resolution, revealing the two RecA-like domains (RecA-like N & RecA-like C) linked with a flexible linker and adopting an open “relaxed” conformation compared to RNA-bound DDX3X structure reported in the literature (**Fig. 3B, C**). A clear density was observed for ADP molecule within the ADP-binding pocket of DDX1 RecA-Like N domain.

Figure 3. Structural characterization of Human DDX1 helicase. **(A)** Domain organization of human DDX1 helicase. **(B)** Crystal structure of the Human DDX1 helicase in complex with ADP (PDB ID: 8TBX). **(C)** Structural superimposition of a closed state DDX3X in complex with DNA-RNA hybrid (PDB ID:7LIU) and DDX1 in open state.

Biochemical Assay

ATPase Activity Assay

Helicases utilize the energy derived from ATP hydrolysis for duplex DNA/RNA unwinding. DDX1 helicase was shown to unwind both duplex RNA and DNA-RNA hybrid structures *in vitro*. Here, we developed a high-throughput DDX1 ATPase activity assay (28). The assay uses a 24-mer dsRNA (GGGACGUCAUGC GCAUGACGUCCC) from IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies, USA) as a substrate and measuring the level of leftover amount of ATP in each reaction using the Kinase-Glo reagent (**Fig. 4A**), which was purchased from Promega (Cat# V6712; Promega, Madison, WI, USA). The reaction mixtures contained 2 μ M ATP and 100 nM of 24-mer ds-RNA in 20 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5, 0.01 % Tween 20, 1 mM MgCl₂, and 2 mM DTT), with a final volume of 15 μ L per well. The reactions were initiated by adding DDX1 at final concentrations of 100 nM. The reaction mixtures were incubated for 30–60 min, and then quenched by adding 15 μ L of luciferase reagent mix to each well. Subsequently, 25 μ L of the mixture from each well was transferred to a 384-well white detection plate and incubated for an additional 15 min before measuring the luminescence signals using a BioTek Synergy 4 plate reader (**Fig. 4B**). The data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and GraphPad Prism 8. We also determined the Z'-factor for DDX1 ATPase assay showing that this assay is amenable for high-throughput screening (**Fig. 4C**).

Figure 4. DDX1 ATPase activity assay for compound screening. **(A)** Schematic overview of ATPase activity assay. **(B)** Detection of DDX1 ATPase activity using bioluminescence assay. The addition of dsRNA promotes DDX1 ATPase activity in a concentration dependent manner. **(C)** Z'-factor determination for DDX1. The activity RLU without DDX1 (■) and with DDX1 (●) wells. Z'-factor calculated as previously described (29).

Unwinding Activity Assay

To measure the enzymatic activity of DDX1 to unwind RNA-DNA duplexes, a fluorescence-based unwinding assay was developed to measure the presence and absence of these duplexes after exposure to active DDX1. Specific reaction conditions are listed in the Materials and Methods section under Additional Information and were based on an initial unwinding assay developed by Li and colleagues (5). A 29-nt, Fluorescein Amidite (FAM)-labeled DNA oligonucleotide (D29 5'-FAM) was annealed to a complementary, 29-nt, Black Hole Quencher-1 (BHQ1)-labeled RNA oligonucleotide (R29 3'-BHQ1) at a 1:1.2 molar ratio in Annealing Buffer by heating to 95° C for 2 min and then slowly cooling to room temperature for 2 hrs. Once annealed, the BHQ1 label quenches the fluorescent signal from FAM resulting in a depletion of signal as compared to D29 5'-FAM alone. Unlabeled DNA nucleotide (D29-none) can outcompete D29 5'-FAM to bind with R29 3'-BHQ1 after unwinding of the duplex by DDX1 in the presence of ADP, thus freeing the D29 5'-FAM to fluoresce (**Fig. 5A**). Measurement of fluorescence of the DNA, RNA, and RNA-DNA duplexes demonstrated effective quenching of the FAM signal when D29 5'-FAM and R29 3'-BHQ1 were duplexed (**Fig. 5B**).

Figure 5. (A) Schematic of DDX1 unwinding assay. The 29-nt, Fluorescein Amidite (FAM)-labeled DNA oligonucleotide (D29 5'-FAM) fluoresces when free but when annealed to a complementary, 29-nt, Black Hole Quencher-1 (BHQ1)-labeled RNA oligonucleotide (R29 3'-BHQ1), the fluorescence is quenched. When DDX1 added the annealed oligonucleotides along with an unlabeled version of the 29-nt DNA oligonucleotide (D29-none), the annealed RNA:DNA structure can be unwound. The free D29-none can replace the labeled D29 5'-FAM in annealed structures, and thus, freeing some D29 5'-FAM strands which then produce a fluorescent signal (**B**) Fluorescence intensity of free and annealed RNA and DNA oligonucleotides before the DDX1 unwinding assay.

The DDX1 unwinding assay was developed for a 384-well format in a total volume of 10 μL and is suitable for future high-throughput screening (HTS). The DDX1 protein was expressed and purified from full-length biotinylated DDX1 (PBC037A10) as described in the protein purification methods. The purified DDX1 (100 μM) and R29 3'BHQ1:D29 5'-FAM duplexes (80 nM) plus or minus D29-none (5 μM) were incubated with ADP (1 mM) were incubated at room temperature (**Fig. 6A**) in Unwinding Buffer. DDX1 unwinding is ADP dependent. Fluorescence emission from 6-FAM was read at 520 nM following excitation at 480 nM and is represented as fluorescence intensity (FI). The FI signal of unwinding activity is time- and dose-dependently increased with DDX1 protein when activity is measured at 50 and 100 μM DDX1 across the first 60 min after ADP addition (**Fig. 6B**) and after an overnight, room temperature incubation with increasing concentrations of DDX1 (**Fig. 6C**). Furthermore, the FI signal of helicase activity is time- and dose-dependently increased with RNA-DNA complex when measured across the first 120 min of reaction (**Fig. 6D**) and when measured across

Figure 6. (A) Schematic of 384-well format DDX1 unwinding assay. **(B)** Kinetic reading of DDX1 unwinding activity across time at 50 and 100 μM DDX1 over 60 min (100 μM annealed RNA:DNA). **(C)** Dose-response curve of DDX1 activity across varying DDX1 concentrations and reaction conditions following O/N incubation at RT. **(D)** Kinetic reading of DDX1 unwinding activity across time at 100 μM DDX1 with 80 nM annealed RNA:DNA over 120 min. **(E)** Fluorescent intensity of DDX1 unwinding assay at noted annealed RNA:DNA and D29-none concentrations following and overnight incubation at RT. **(F)** S/B for (E). **(G)** Z' for (E).

increasing RNA-DNA duplex concentrations after an overnight, room temperature incubation. The assay was further optimized by testing two concentrations of D29-none across concentrations of R29 3'BHQ1:D29 5'-FAM duplexes when incubated overnight at room temperature with 80 μM DDX1 (**Fig. 6E**). The assay parameters S/B (signal to background) and Z' were calculated to assess the DDX1 unwinding assay (**Fig 6F, G**). A Z' factor between 0.5 and 1 indicates a robust assay that is suitable for HTS. S/B is an indicator of assay sensitivity and the dynamic window of the assay. The final reaction conditions were 100 μM DDX1, 80 nM R29 3'BHQ1:D29 5'-FAM duplexes, 5 μM D29-none, and 1mM ADP were incubated at room temperature for 30-60 minutes in Unwinding Buffer.

See **Additional information (section 2)** for more details.

Biophysical Assay

Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR)

Surface plasma resonance (SPR) was used to measure the binding of compounds to DDX1. SPR measures changes in the refractive index from polarized light hitting a thin metal film on which one binding partner is immobilized. If the analyte molecule is bound to the immobilized molecule, the refractive index changes in a manner quantifiable and detectable in real-time. SPR results are measured by response units (RU), which are proportional to the mass on the sensor surface and to the number of molecules bound to the sensor surface. Response units increase as the analyte molecule binds to the sensor surface.

A putative ligand, HL-622, was identified through virtual screen of the ~ 3.7 million MolPort-2022-03 ligand library using AutoDock Vina, with a threshold of ≤ -8.0 . HL-622 binds to DDX1 with an equilibrium dissociation constant of 20 μM , demonstrating that SPR is a suitable technique for confirming small molecule binding to DDX1 (**Fig. 7**).

Figure 7. Characterization of HL-662 by SPR and ATPase assay. **(A)** IC50 determination was performed by ATPase assay, resulting in an IC50 value of 10 μ M with a Hill Slope of 1.6. **(B-C)** Single-cycle kinetics of HL-662 binding to DDX1 by T200 SPR. **(B)** A representative sensorgram (solid green) is shown with the kinetic fit (black dots). **(C)** The steady-state response (black circles) obtained from (B) is shown with the steady-state 1:1 binding model fitting (red dashed line). From steady-state fitting, KD: 20 μ M, binding activity: 89%.

Differential Scanning Fluorimetry (DSF)

DSF, a technique that measures the melting temperature of protein, is commonly used to assess ligand binding. This method relies on the principle that ligand binding generally stabilizes the folded state of a protein, resulting in a shift in its melting temperature. The melting temperature (T_m) shifts were measured for three DDX1 constructs (RecA-like N, RecA-like C, and full-length) in the presence and absence of ADP (**Fig. 8**). Experiments were conducted using SYPRO Orange dye (Life Technologies, catalog no. S-6650), with fluorescence monitored at 470 nm excitation and 510 nm emission on a LightCycler 480 II (Roche Applied Science).

Samples were prepared in 384-well plates (Axygen; catalog nos. PCR-384-C; UC500) at a final volume of 20 μ l per well, using a buffer containing 50mM HEPES pH7.5, 150mM NaCl, 1mM MgCl₂, 2mM DTT, 0.1 mg/ml DDX1, 500 μ M ADP, and 5 \times SYPRO Orange. Thermal melt curves were recorded from 25 $^{\circ}$ C to 95 $^{\circ}$ C at a 1 $^{\circ}$ C/min gradient, and data were plotted using DSFworld online application for T_m determination. The addition of ADP significantly stabilized DDX1, resulting in a 7.8 $^{\circ}$ C increase in melting temperature for the RecA-like N construct and an 8.6 $^{\circ}$ C increase for the full-length protein. In contrast, the RecA-like C construct showed no thermal stabilization with ADP.

Figure 8. DSF analysis of ADP binding to different constructs (RecA-like N, RecA-like C, and full-length) of DDX1.

Cell-based assays

Knockdown in iPSC neurons

shRNA targeting DDX1 was used to knockdown DDX1 expression in iPSC-derived neurons from the human iPSC lines WTC11 (APOE3/3) and CVi (APOE 3/4). The knockdown was approximately 90% effective in both lines (**Fig. 9A**). Reduction of DDX1 expression did not result in increased cytotoxicity in either line (**Fig. 9B**). Secreted A β 38, A β 40, and A β 42 decreased in the conditioned media with DDX1 knockdown in both lines, but the A β 42/A β 40 ratio did not change (**Fig. 9C**). Total tau and tau phosphorylated at Thr231 (pTau) levels were decreased in the CVi line following DDX1 knockdown but unchanged in the WTC11 neurons (**Fig. 9D**). The pTau/totalTau ratio did not change in either line.

See **Additional information (section 3)** for more details.

Figure 9. (A) Knockdown of DDX1 in CVi- and WTC11-derived neurons confirmed by qPCR in cell lysates as compared to cells transduced with scrambled shRNA as a negative control (n=2 biological replicates x 3 technical replicates). (B) Cytotoxicity as measured by LDH production and detected by the Promega LDH-Glo Cytotoxicity Assay in both lines following DDX1 knockdown (n=2 biological replicates x 3 technical replicates). (C-F) Secreted Aβ38, Aβ40, Aβ42, and Aβ42/Aβ40 ratio in conditioned media from CVi (left) and WTC11 (right) derived neurons (n=2 biological replicates x 2 technical replicates). (G-I) Total tau, pTau, and pTau/totalTau ratio in CVi (left) and WTC11 (right) cell lysates (n=2 biological replicates x 2 technical replicates). *p<0.05, ***p<0.001, n.s.= not significant.

CONCLUSION

DDX1, a DEAD box family RNA helicase, was selected as an AD protein target based on an integrative target ranking score that considered multiple factors. Its disease association was higher when considering genomics from postmortem brain, but genetic risk was also considered. DDX1 protein and RNA expression are altered in brains from AD patients and brain cell subtype expression is also variable. Based on TREAT-AD-defined biodomains, DDX1 is associated with the RNA spliceosome, immune response, and DNA repair and its inhibition is predicted to be therapeutically beneficial. To enable study of this protein, we validated

DDX1 antibodies from various sources using a DDX1 knockout cell line and generated an antibody characterization report. We also produced full-length, human DDX1 and solved the first ADP-bound crystal structure at a 2.7 Å resolution. Enabled by the in-hand protein, we developed DDX1 ATPase and DDX1 unwinding activity assays. Finally, to enable biophysical characterization of the binding of small molecules, we employed surface plasmon resonance (SPR) and differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF). This portfolio of reagents and assays, which is available to the broader scientific community, has been summarized in this TEP and is being used in a medicinal chemistry program to develop chemical probes to interrogate potential roles of DDX1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

1. Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. Full length His-tagged DDX1

Sample ID	PBC037-A07
Purpose	DSF & ATPase assay
Vector	pFBOH-MHL
AA start to end	1-740
N-terminal tag	MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQG
C-terminal tag	N/A
Expected Mass (Da)	84625.49
Protein sequence	MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQGMAAFSEMGMPEIAQAVEEMDWLLPTDIQAESIPLILGGGDV LMAAETGSGKTGAFSIPVIQIVYETLKDQQEGKKGKTTIKTGASVLNKWQMNPYDRGSAFAI GSDGLCCQSREVKWEWHGCRATKGLMKGKHYYEVSCHDQGLCRVWSTMQASLDLGTDKF GFGFGGTGKKSHNKQFDNYGEEFTMHDITIGCYLDIDKGHVKFSKNGKDLGLAFEIPPHMKN QALFPACVLKNAELKFNFGEEEFKFPKDGVALSKAPDGYIVKSQHSNAQVTQTKFLPNAP KALIVEPSRELAEQTLNNIKQFKKYIDNPKLRELLIIGGVAARDQLSVLENGVDIVVGTGRLDD

LVSTGKLNLSQVRFLVLDEADGLLSQGYSDFINRMHNQIPQVTS DGKRLQVIVCSATLHSFDV
 KKLSEKIMHFPTWVDLKGEDSVPDTVHHVVVPVNPKTDRLWERLGKSHIRTTDDVHAKDNTR
 PGANSPBMWSEAIKILKGEYAVRAIKEHKMDQAIIFCRTKIDCDNLEQYFIQQGGGPDKKGH
 QFSCVCLHGDRKPKHERKQNLERFKKGDVRFICTDVAARGIDIHGVPYVINVTLPDEKQNYVH
 RIGRVGRAERMGLAISLVATEKEKVWYHVCSSRGKGCYNTRLKEDGGCTIWYNEMQLLSEIE
 EHLNCTISQVEPDIKVPVDFDVGKVTYQGKRAAGGGSYKGHVDILAPTQELAALEKEAQTSE
 LHLGYLPNQLFRTE

Purified protein (PBC037A07)	
IMAC, Ni (step 1):	
SEC (step 2):	
Intact mass deconvolution (Da):	<p>84671</p>
Protein yield:	3.7 mg/L culture

Expression and purification protocol	<p>The wild-type gene of DDX1 (1-740aa) was PCR amplified and subcloned into pFBOH-MHL vector. The plasmids were transformed into DH10Bac™ Competent E. coli (Invitrogen) and a recombinant viral bacmid DNA was purified, followed by a recombinant baculovirus generation for baculovirus mediated protein production in Sf9 insect cells (30). The Cells were harvested 72-96 h post-infection and resuspended in 20 mM Tris-HCL, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1X protease inhibitor cocktail (100 X protease inhibitor stock in 70% ethanol (0.25 mg/mL Aprotinin, 0.25 mg/mL Leupeptin, 0.25 mg/mL Pepstatin A and 0.25 mg/mL E-64). The cells were lysed chemically with 0.5% NP40 and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 7.0 (5" on/7" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was first washed with 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 5 mM imidazole. A second wash with the same buffer containing 1 M NaCl and 5 mM imidazole was performed to remove bound nucleic acids. A third wash with 30 mM imidazole and 500 mM NaCl was applied, and the target protein was finally eluted with 250 mM imidazole in the same buffer. The eluted protein was supplemented with 2mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 300 mM NaCl, 2 mM TCEP. The pure fractions were pooled together and concentrated</p>
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2. ΔSPRY_CTD

Sample ID	PBC037-A11
Purpose	Crystallization trial
Vector	pFBOH-MHL
AA start to end	1-674; Δ75-285
N-terminal tag	MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQG
C-terminal tag	N/A
Expected Mass (Da)	54457.11
Protein sequence	<p>MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQGMAAFSEMGVMPEIAQAVEEMDWLLPTDIAESIPLILGGGDV LMAAETGSGKTGAFSIPVIQIVYETLKDQQEG_sgs_sgs_APKALIVEPSRELAEQTLNNIKQFKK YIDNPKLRELLIIGGVAARDQLSVLENGVDIVVGTGRLDDLVTGKLNLSQVRFLVLDEADGLL SQGYSDFINRMHNPQVTSQDGRKLVIVCSATLHSDVKKLSEKIMHFPTWVDLKGEDSVP DTVHHVVVPVNPKTDRWLWRLGKSHIRTDVHAKDNTRPGANSPMWSAIIKILKGEYAVR AIKEHKMDQAIIFCRTKIDCDNLEQYFIQQGGGPDKKGHQFSCVCLHGDRKPKHERKQNLERF</p>

KKGDVRFLECTDVAARGIDIHGVPYVINVTLPDEKQNYVHRIGRVGRAERMGLAISLVATEKEK
 VWHVHCSSRGKGCYNTRLKEDGGCTIWYNEMQLLSEIEEHLNCTISQVE

Purified protein (PBC037A11)

IMAC, Ni (step 1):

SEC (step 2):

Overnight TEV cleavage

Source 30Q

Intact mass deconvolution (Da):	52366
Protein yield:	16.8 mg/L culture
Expression and purification protocol	<p>The ΔSPRY_CTD (aa286-674) truncated gene construct were PCR amplified and subcloned into pFBOH-MHL vector. The plasmids were transformed into DH10Bac™ Competent E. coli (Invitrogen) and a recombinant viral bacmid DNA was purified, followed by a recombinant baculovirus generation for baculovirus mediated protein production in Sf9 insect cells (30). The cells were harvested 72-96 h post-infection and resuspended in 20 mM Tris-HCL, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1X protease inhibitor cocktail (100 X protease inhibitor stock in 70% ethanol (0.25 mg/mL Aprotinin, 0.25 mg/mL Leupeptin, 0.25 mg/mL Pepstatin A and 0.25 mg/mL E-64). The cells were lysed chemically with 0.5% NP40 and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 7.0 (5" on/7" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was first washed with 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 5 mM imidazole. A second wash using the same buffer with 25 mM imidazole was applied, and the target protein was finally eluted with 250 mM imidazole in the same buffer. The eluted protein was supplemented with 2mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 300 mM NaCl, 2 mM TCEP. Proteins were pooled and incubated overnight at 4 °C with tobacco etch virus protease (TEV) to cleave the His6 tag. The protein was further purified by cation exchange chromatography using a Source 30Q column pre-equilibrated with 20 mM Tris, pH 7.5 and eluted with 20 mM Tris, pH 7.5 at a concentration gradient of 1 M NaCl. The pure fractions were pooled together, supplemented with 2mM TCEP and 1,2-propanediol, and concentrated.</p>

3. RecA-like N

Sample ID	PBC035-B11
Purpose	DSF
Vector	pET28-MHL
AA start to end	1-431; Δ 75-285
N-terminal tag	MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQG
C-terminal tag	N/A

Expected Mass (Da)	24578
Protein sequence	MHHHHHSSGRENLYFQGMAAFSEMGMPEIAQAVEEMDWLLPTDIQAESIPLILGGGDV LMAAETGSGKTGAFSIPVIQIVYETLKDQOEG_sgsgsg_APKALIVEPSRELAEQTLNNIKQFKK YIDNPKLRELLIIGGVAARDQLSVLENGVDIVVGTGRLDDLSTGKLNLSQVRFLVLDEADGLL SQGYSDFINRMHNQIPQVTS DGKRLQVIVCSATLHSFDVKKLSEKIMHFPTWVDL

Purified protein (PBC035B11)	
IMAC, Ni (step 1):	<p>DDX1_RecA-D1_Ecoli Ni profile. Apr 25/2023</p> <p>FT W1 W2 W3 E1 E2 E3 E4.MW</p> <p>From 2L culture 2mL beads/L culture. W1: Lysis b. W2: Imi30mM W3:NaCl, E2 to E4 for TEV and dialysis.</p>
Dialysis & TEV cleavage (step 2):	<p>TEV cleavage</p> <p>MW, uncut, cut 1:20, cut 1:4</p>

<p>SEC (step 3):</p>	<p>DDX1 GF profile. Apr 26/2023</p> <p>20Tris8 300NaCl Collected: G8 to H5, 10,6 mg/mL, 47.7mg</p>
<p>Intact mass deconvolution (Da):</p>	<p>Full Range</p> <p>24579</p>
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>23.85 mg/L culture</p>
<p>Expression and purification protocol</p>	<p>The truncated gene construct of DDX1 (aa1-431; Δ75-285) was PCR amplified and subcloned into the pET28-MHL vector. The His6-tagged proteins were expressed in E. coli BL21 (DE3) codon plus RIL strain (Stratagene) with the supplementation of 1 mM isopropyl-1-thio-D-galactopyranoside overnight at 15°C. Harvested cells were resuspended in 20 mM Tris, pH 8, 250 mM NaCl, 5 mM imidazole and 5% glycerol. The cells were lysed chemically with 0.1% CHAPS, 1 mM phenylmethyl sulfonyl fluoride, and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 8.5 (10" on/10" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was first washed with 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 250 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 5 mM imidazole. A second wash with the same buffer containing 1 M NaCl and 5 mM imidazole was performed to remove bound nucleic acids. A third wash with 30 mM imidazole and 250 mM NaCl was applied,</p>

	and the target protein was finally eluted with 250 mM imidazole in the same buffer. The eluted protein was then dialyzed overnight into 20 mM Tris pH 8, 0.5 M NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 10 mM β -mercaptoethanol in the presence of TEV protease to remove the polyhistidine (His6) tag. The protein was then further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Tris, pH 8, 300 mM NaCl. The pure fractions were pooled together, supplemented with 1mM TCEP.
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4. RecA-like C

Sample ID	PBC035B12
Purpose	DSF
Vector	pET28-MHL
AA start to end	433-674
N-terminal tag	MHHHHHSSGRENLYFQG
C-terminal tag	N/A
Expected Mass (Da)	27632.45
Protein sequence	MHHHHHSSGRENLYFQGGEDSVPDTVHHVVVPVNPKTDRWLWRLGKSHIRTDDVHAKD NTRPGANSPPEMWSEAIKILKGEYAVRAIKEHKMDQAIIFCRTKIDCDNLEQYFIQQGGGPDKK GHQFSCVCLHGDRKPKHERKQNLERFKKGDVRFLECTDVAARGIDIHGVPYVINVTLPDEKQNY VHRIGRVGRAERMGLAISLVATEKEKVVYHVCSSRGKGCYNTRLKEDGGCTIWYNEMQLLS EIEEHLNCTISQVE

Purified protein (PBC035B12)

<p>IMAC, Ni (step 1):</p>	<p>DDX1_RecA-D2_Ecoli Ni profile. Apr 26/2023</p> <p>From 2L culture 2mL beads/L culture. W1: Lysis b. W2: Imi30mM W3:NaCl, E3 to E6 for TEV and dialysis.</p>
<p>Dialysis/ TEV cleavage overnight & reverse Ni (step 2&3):</p>	<p>TEV cleavage, Reverse Ni</p> <p>1: uncut 2: cut, before Reverse Ni 3: cut, after Reverse Ni 4: cut, FT 5: cut, Afer Reverse Ni, beads (Samples diluted 1:4, load 5ul)</p>

<p>SEC (step 3):</p>	<p>DDX1 GF profile. Apr 27/2023</p>
<p>Intact mass deconvolution (Da):</p>	<p>Deconvoluted Spectra</p> <p>27690</p>
<p>Expression and purification protocol</p>	<p>The truncated gene construct of DDX1 (aa1-431; Δ75-285) was PCR amplified and subcloned into the pET28-MHL vector. The His6-tagged proteins were expressed in <i>E. coli</i> BL21 (DE3) codon plus RIL strain (Stratagene) with the supplementation of 1 mM isopropyl-1-thio-D-galactopyranoside overnight at 15°C. Harvested cells were resuspended in 20 mM Hepes, pH 7, 250 mM NaCl, 5 mM imidazole and 5% glycerol. The cells were lysed chemically with 0.1% CHAPS, 1 mM phenylmethyl sulfonyl fluoride, and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 8.5 (10" on/10" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was first washed with 20 mM Hepes, pH 7, 250 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 5 mM imidazole. A second wash with the same buffer containing 1 M NaCl and 5 mM imidazole was performed to remove bound</p>

	nucleic acids. A third wash with 30 mM imidazole and 250 mM NaCl was applied, and the target protein was finally eluted with 250 mM imidazole in the same buffer. The eluted protein was then dialyzed overnight into 20 mM Hepes pH 7, 0.5 M NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 10 mM β -mercaptoethanol in the presence of TEV protease to remove the polyhistidine (His6) tag. The uncut fraction of the protein was removed the following day by passing it through the Nickel affinity resin in an open column, and the flow-through (cleaved protein) was collected. Protein was then further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Hepes, pH 7, 300 mM NaCl. The pure fractions were pooled together, supplemented with 1mM TCEP.
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5. Full-length biotinylated DDX1

Sample ID	PBC037A10
Purpose	SPR
Vector	pFBD-BirA
AA start to end	1-740
N-terminal tag	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
C-terminal tag	GGSGHHHHHH
Expected Mass (Da)	86015.92
Protein sequence	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGMAAFSEMGMPEIAQAVEEMDWLLPTDIQAESILIL GGGDVLMAAETGSGKTGAFSIPVIQIVYETLKDQQEGKKGKTTIKTGASVLNKWQMNPYDR GSAFAIGSDGLCCQSREVKWEWHGCRATKGLMKGKHYYEVSCHDQGLCRVWSTMQASLDL GTDKFGFGFGGTGKKSHNKQFDNYGEEFTMHDITIGCYLDIDKGHVKFSKNGKDLGLAFEIPP HMKNQALFPACVLKNAELKFNFGEEEFKPPKDGVALSKAPDGYIVKSQHSNGNAQVTQTKF LPNAPKALIVEPSRELAEQTLNNIKQFKKYIDNPKLRELLIIGGVAARDQLSVLENGVDIVGTP GRLDDLSTGKLNLSQVRFLVLDEADGLLSQGYSDFINRMHNQIPQVTS DGKRLQVIVCSATL HSFDVKKLSEKIMHFPTWVDLKGEDSVPDTHHHVVPVNPKTDRWLWRLGKSHIRTDVHA KDNRPGANSPBMWSEAIKILKGEYAVRAIKEHKMDQAIIFCRTKIDCDNLEQYFIQQGGGPD KKGHQFSCVCLHGDRKPKHERKQNLERFKKGDVRFICTDVAARGIDIHGVPYVINVTLPDEKQ NYVHRIGRVGRAERMGLAISLVATEKEKVVYHVCSSRGKGCYNTRLKEDGGCTIWYNEMQL LSEIEEHLNCTISQVEPDIKVPVDFDQKVTYQKRAAGGGSYKGHVDILAPTVQELAALEKEA QTSFLHLGYLPNQLFRFTFGGSGHHHHHH

Purified protein (PBC037A10)

<p>IMAC, Ni (step 1):</p>	<p>Ni-NTA profile.</p> <p>From 4L culture, CV3. W1:Lysis buffer ,W2:1MNaCl, 1 to 4: Imi30mM. Elutions: E1 to E5. Collect: E1 to E3</p>
<p>SEC (step 2):</p>	<p>GF profile. S200</p>
<p>Intact mass deconvolution (Da):</p>	<p>NA</p>
<p>Expression and purification protocol:</p>	<p>The full-length DDX1 was also cloned into the pFBD-BirA expression vector. pFBD-BirA is a derivative of pFastBac Dual (Invitrogen) that coexpresses biotin ligase and adds an N-terminal biotin acceptor peptide and a C-terminal 6X His-tag to DDX1. The plasmids were transformed into DH10Bac™ Competent E. coli (Invitrogen) and a recombinant viral bacmid DNA was purified, followed by a recombinant baculovirus generation for baculovirus mediated protein production in Sf9 insect cells (30). Production of the biotinylated-DDX1 was done with addition into baculovirus-infected Sf9 cells cultured in D-biotin (Sigma-Aldrich) to the final concentration of 10 µg/mL.</p> <p>The Cells were harvested 72-96 h post-infection and resuspended in 20 mM Tris-HCL, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1X protease inhibitor cocktail (100 X protease</p>

inhibitor stock in 70% ethanol (0.25 mg/mL Aprotinin, 0.25 mg/mL Leupeptin, 0.25 mg/mL Pepstatin A and 0.25 mg/mL E-64). The cells were lysed chemically with 0.5% NP40 and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 7.0 (5" on/7" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was first washed with 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 5 mM imidazole. A second wash with the same buffer containing 1 M NaCl and 5 mM imidazole was performed to remove bound nucleic acids. A third wash with 30 mM imidazole and 500 mM NaCl was applied, and the target protein was finally eluted with 250 mM imidazole in the same buffer. The eluted protein was supplemented with 2mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 300 mM NaCl. The pure fractions were pooled together and supplemented with 1mM TCEP.

2. Unwinding Activity Assay

Buffer Recipes

Annealing Buffer: 20 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 200 mM potassium acetate, and 0.1 mM EDTA.

Unwinding Buffer: 20 mM Tris-HCl (pH7.5), 70 mM KCl, 2 mM magnesium acetate, 1.5 mM dithiothreitol, 10 U of RNAase inhibitor

Oligonucleotide sequences

D29 5'-FAM: /56-FAM/GC ATG CCT GCA GGT CGA CTC TAG AGG ATC (Integrated DNA Technologies, Inc)

D29-none: GCA TGC CTG CAG GTC GAC TCT AGA GGA TC (Integrated DNA Technologies, Inc)

R29 3'-BHQ1: rGrArU rCrCrU rCrUrA rGrArG rUrCrG rArCrC rUrGrC rArGrG rCrArU rGrC/3BHQ_1 (Bio-Synthesis Inc)

Formulas

$$S/B = FL_{\text{sample}}/FL_{\text{background}}$$

$$Z' = (3*SD_{\text{sample}} + 3*SD_{\text{background}}) / (FL_{\text{control}} - FL_{\text{background}})$$

FL_{sample} is the mean fluorescence intensity signal from R29 3'BHQ1:D29 5'-FAM, D29-none, ADP, and DDX1 at each condition, and SD_{sample} is the standard deviation of this signal.

$FL_{\text{background}}$ is the mean fluorescence intensity signal from annealed R29 3'BHQ1:D29 5'-FAM, D29-none, and ADP incubated without DDX1 protein, and $SD_{\text{background}}$ is the standard deviation of this signal.

3. Knockdown in iPSC neurons

iPSC cell culture, differentiation, and knockdown protocols

For more information or questions regarding the TEP, please contact treatad.info@sagebionetworks.org

The WTC11 iPSC line (31) and the CVi iPSC line (32) were cultured and differentiated into neurons by the dual SMAD protocol as previously described (33). Following differentiation, iPSC neurons were passaged to Matrigel-coated 96 well culture plates for shRNA knockdown. iPSC derived neurons were infected with shRNA-containing lentivirus (MOI 5) on Day 2 following neuronal passaging. The cells were cultured with the lentivirus for 72 hours before replacing the media with fresh media. Conditioned medium and cell protein lysates were then harvested for experimental studies following an additional 72 hours. Viral transduction was confirmed by GFP fluorescence. Knockdown efficiency was confirmed by qPCR.

shDDX1 sequence

GATGTGGTCTGAAGCTATTA

Cell phenotypic measurements following DDX1 knockdown

Cells were plated at 250,000 cells/well in a 96 well plate. Media was collected from each well following 72 hours of conditioning to measure secreted A β and cytotoxicity. Protein was harvested according to manufacturer's specifications (Meso Scale Discovery Cat. No. K15121D-2) from corresponding cell lysates for measurements of intracellular tau. Cytotoxicity was measured by the Promega LDH-Glo Cytotoxicity Assay. A β was measured by the Meso Scale Discovery V-PLEX A β Peptide Panel 1 (6E10) Kit (Cat. No. K15200E-2). Total tau and pTau (Thre231) were measured by the Meso Scale Discovery Phospho(Thr231)/Total tau Kit in cell lysates 6 days post transduction (Cat. No. K15121D-2).

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